

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Bhideshwari, a new rice variety for rainfed wetland areas in Nepal

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Bhideshwari (IET1444), obtained through a TN1 / CO 29 cross in India, was introduced in Nepal through the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery in 1975. In tests under wetland conditions, it averaged 3.6 t/ha at 6 irrigated sites and 3.5 t/ha at 7 rainfed sites. Under rainfed dryland conditions at 3 sites over 3 years, it averaged

2.7 t/ha. In farmers' fields, it averaged 3.2 t/ha.

Disease resistance was high, with ratings (Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale) of 3 for bacterial blight, 5 for brown spot, and 3 for blast. Bhideshwari matures in 105 days and is 85 cm high. Protein-content is 8%.

The variety release committee of the Department of Agriculture, Nepal, has released Bhideshwari for areas at altitudes of 914 m under varying growth conditions. Because almost all previous varieties were recommended for irrigated conditions and high inputs, a large area is expected to be planted to Bhideshwari in the future. ■

Induced rice mutants in Haryana

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Using doses of physical (r rays) and chemical (DES, EMS) mutagens, singly and in combination, we rectified some

of the genetic defects in three most commonly cultivated rices: Basmati 370, Jhona 349, and IR8. Plant progeny performance of 40 mutants led to the selection of 2 mutants of Basmati that are earlier maturing and higher yielding than the initial line (see table). But grain fineness is much reduced.

Two Jhona mutants with much

Characteristics of rice mutants in Haryana.^a

	Shoot ht (cm)	Maturity in days	Grain yield (g)	Grain fineness (length:breadth)	Protein content (%)
Basmati 370 (control)	147.1 ± 0.67	148.98 ± 0.91	16.1 ± 0.36	3.61 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 0.08
Bm3	122.1 ± 0.90	132.15 ± 0.95	21.4 ± 0.55	2.82 ± 0.01	7.4 ± 0.05
Bm4	116.7 ± 0.59	130.69 ± 0.88	21.3 ± 0.52	2.76 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.04
CD at 5% level	4.79	6.34	1.25	0.05	0.05
Jhona 349 (control)	132.5 ± 0.54	125.16 ± 0.71	20.4 ± 0.59	3.00 ± 0.02	7.3 ± 0.04
Jm2	128.7 ± 0.69	124.72 ± 0.82	22.8 ± 0.61	3.51 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.09
Jm3	137.2 ± 0.70	123.29 ± 0.75	20.6 ± 0.61	3.52 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.08
CD at 5% level	4.69	5.78	1.25	0.05	0.06
IR8 (control)	87.8 ± 0.04	150.90 ± 1.38	20.6 ± 0.36	2.38 ± 0.01	7.1 ± 0.04
IRm1	118.2 ± 0.80	124.19 ± 1.85	22.6 ± 0.36	2.82 ± 0.02	8.2 ± 0.06
IRm6	85.7 ± 0.40	131.68 ± 1.48	20.8 ± 0.26	2.62 ± 0.01	8.7 ± 0.05
CD at 5% level	5.43	7.42	1.03	0.04	0.07

^aMean values of 360 plants, M₅-M₇ generations. ±: standard error.

Seed protein (% of initial line)

Total seed protein production of rice mutants. Haryana, India.

higher grain yield and whose fineness matches that of Basmati 370 have been developed. A recombinant with superfine grain is being tested. Two early, fine-grained, higher yielding mutants of IR8 also have been obtained.

Seed protein production of all these mutants is much higher than that of their corresponding initial lines (see figure). The mutants have been tested for performance, stability, and adaptability for four generations. ■

Improvement of local rice varieties by pureline selection in Afghanistan

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Rice is the third most important cereal crop in Afghanistan, covering 2 10,000 hectares, 16.6% of the total cropped area. Rice cultivation is concentrated in two zones — Nangarhar in the East with 34% and Baghlan in the North with 43% of the total rice area.

Almost all the rice area is planted to indigenous varieties of high quality with long slender translucent grains, but they seem badly mixed. Local varieties are tall growing with weak stems and are prone to lodging. They respond poorly to fertilization, with the result that the average rice yield is stabilized at about 2 t/ha.

The important, good quality commercial rice varieties are Barah, Mahin, Lawangin, Basmati, and Dehraduni.

Performance of promising strains developed by pureline selection from local varieties at the Sheesham Bagh Agricultural Research Station, Jalalabad.

Commercial variety	Strain no.	Av yield (t/ha) 1975-78	Increase over bulk	
			kg/ha	%
Barah	5	3.3	801	31.5
	12	3.0	436	17.2
	Bulk	2.5	—	—
Mahin	2	2.8	68	2.5
	15	2.8	65	2.4
	27	3.1	311	11.3
	Bulk	2.8	—	—
Lawangin	11	3.1	549	17.7
	16	3.5	438	14.1
	Bulk	3.1	—	—
Basmati	3	2.9	32	1.1
	6	3.5	692	23.8
	Bulk	2.9	—	—
Dehraduni	8	2.5	357	16.5
	12	3.0	826	38.1
	21	3.5	1311	60.5
	Bulk	2.2	—	—

They have been grown since time immemorial without attempts to bring about varietal improvement. Each variety is a mixture of a number of morphologically similar lines. Systematic pureline selection work was initiated in 1972 at the Sheesham Bagh Agricultural Research Station, Jalalabad, Nangarhar.

Single plant progenies were compared with bulk varieties. Pure breeding and promising strains were further tested in 2-4 year replicated varietal trials 1975-

1978. Two to three best quality and yield strains have been selected in each variety.

The new strains yielded an average 32 kg/ha (1.12%) to 1311 kg/ha (60.51%) more than their respective bulk varieties (see table). Strains No. 5 in Barah, No. 27 in Mahin, No. 11 in Lawangin, No. 6 in Basmati, and No. 21 in Dehraduni have been selected for further multiplication to replace local commercial varieties. ■

Performance of direct-sown photo-period-sensitive rices at varying nitrogen levels under shallow-deep water at North Bihar, India

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A field trial during the 1980 wet season at the Rajendra Agricultural University Farm, Pusa, was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. Three nitrogen levels (0, 20, and 40 kg/ha) were assigned to main plots and 7 varieties (64-117, 62-68, 62-31, 62-10, BR14, Parwapankh, and Akalbir) were assigned to subplots. Soil type was clay loam with 0.7% organic carbon, 11.2 kg available P₂O₅/ha, and 208 kg available K₂O/ha. The pH was 8.4 and the EC 0.35 mmho/cm.

Seeds were drilled 21 May in rows 20 cm apart, at a rate of 80 kg seed/ha. After weeding the first week of July, nitrogen through urea was applied as top-dressing. Rainwater from catchments started accumulating the last week of July and maximum water depth went to 81 cm in late August. Harvest was in early December.

64-117 and Parwapankh had significantly higher yields than other varieties (see table). High yields were due to more panicles and a higher grain weight (resulting in heavier panicles) in 64-117, and a higher number of spikelets per panicle and higher spikelet fertility in Parwapankh. Maximum plant height was recorded in Akalbir, indicating it may be suitable for medium-deepwater areas.

Neither grain yield nor any other plant characteristics were influenced sig-